

Study of Consumer Buying behaviour of Online Marketing of FMCG Products

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Abstract: -

FMCG sector or Consumer packaged goods (CPG) are referred to products which are being sold at a very low cost. Although profitability of various FMCG products has been quite small but they are sold in huge quantities, hence the overall profit on FMCG products would be high. FMCG industry in India is considered to be fourth largest sector in economy and it is expected that it scales upto Rs 1,300 crores. During past ten years, annual growth rate in industry has been 11%. Sale of unbranded FMCG products as well as unpackaged products are also being sold in the market not only in the rural areas but also in the urban areas. The main segments of FMCG industry are said to be personal care, food and beverage and household care.

Key-Words: - FMCG, ITC, HUL.

Introduction: -

Benefits of shopping FMCG products online

Online shopping of FMCG products has been beneficial to the consumers due to the following reasons:

Changing lifestyle – The consumers are changing their way of shopping online and now they prefer to buy FMCG products and others online itself. Instead of going to a physical store, the consumers prefer to buy goods online as they are quite busy in their regular work and those goods which are required regularly are preferably bought online.

1) Convenient – Online shopping of FMCG products has become quite easy and consumers could buy FMCG products online through mobile or laptop or desktop.

Consumers are making more use of mobile phone for placing online orders for FMCG products rather than visiting a physical store.

2) Comparison – The FMCG products could be easily compared among the products which are available through different e-commerce websites. The price, quantity and quality could be compared and then order could be placed for buying FMCG products online.

3) Discounts – Some FMCG companies provide discount when FMCG products are bought online in bulk or when the total amount being spent online for buying FMCG products surpasses a certain amount like Rs. 500 or more.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of research

- a) To evaluate the level of satisfaction towards shopping of FMCG products online
- b) To find out the Monthly expenses for buying FMCG products online
- c) To understand the association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Kansal (2015) have studied influence of brand on buying of FMCG products. The result of the study indicated that different variables like gender, income, occupation, family size and educational qualification is having a positive correlation with an impact on online buying of FMCG products. Free gifts and cash discount are considered to be a scheme being used for promotion by marketers.

Anandrajan (2016) have discussed about expectations of the consumers towards FMCG products in the Villupuram district. This study is based on primary data which has been collected through face to face interview with consumers. This study has analyzed socio-economic background of respondents as well as satisfaction level. Consumers are buying products only when they get attracted towards them.

Qazzafi S. (2019) has explained about the buying process being followed by the consumers. This study aimed to evaluate the pattern which the consumers are following while they make purchases of any product. The study is based on secondary data which has been considered from different sources like books, articles, websites and research

papers. This study concluded that consumers have been purchasing products when they are in need of them and they follow a decision procedure which involves certain stages. There is more involvement of the customers when the product is bit costly. All products do not involve all the steps, it depends upon the cost of the product.

Jaganathan A. T. & Sakthivel M. (2021) have tried to gain an understanding about the influence which the buying behaviour of consumers have on GST which is being levied on FMCG. The area of study is Namakkal district which is located in Tamil Nadu. The findings concluded FMCG organic good after applying GST. The study focused on observing factor that influence the consumers while they purchase FMCG organic product. A sample comprising of 240 respondents has been considered. ANOVA is applied for testing the hypothesis. This study concluded that there is existence of link between influential level of FMCG organic food items after the application of GST. **Priyadharshini T. & Karthick P. (2021)** have mentioned in study that changes have come up in buying preference of the consumers and there has been different reasons for making use of technology in making and selling the products. Primary data has been collected to understand the awareness about different brands among the people. Analysis has been done with the use of simple percentage. This particular study has helped in identification of different factors which actually impact the buying decision of different electronic goods. 120 respondents have been considered as a sample and the sample has been selected through the use of convenience sampling method. This study concluded that FMCG goods and services are preferred based on the quality and loyalty.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

- H_{01} - There is no significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers
 H_{11} - There is a significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers
- H_{02} - There is no significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products

H₂₂ - There is a significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study is descriptive in nature as it is based on the consumers who have been buying FMCG products online through an application or through e-commerce website. This study is based on primary data which has been collected through structured questionnaire based on consumers buying behaviour towards FMCG products. In this study, FMCG companies considered are ITC and HUL. Response from the customers has been considered towards FMCG products of ITC and HUL as they are the leaders in the FMCG sector.

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

a) **Primary data-** This study is mainly based on primary data which has been collected through a structured questionnaire which has been designed on the basis of the objectives and hypothesis of the study. This questionnaire contains questions which helps in finding out the online buying behavior of the consumers towards FMCG products. The collected data has been further analyzed through the use of SPSS 20.

b) **Secondary data-** This study has also involved secondary data which has been collected from websites, books, journals, newspapers etc. for deeper understanding about the online buying behavior of consumers.

RESEARCH SAMPLE

- **Sampling Plan-** A sample of 120 has been considered in the study for evaluating the online buying behaviour of the consumers. The consumers considered in the study are located in Alwar.
- **Sampling Technique-** This study deals with the consumers who have been buying FMCG products online and the sampling technique used in this study is convenience sampling. As a small sample is selected from a huge population hence it is collected by convenience sampling.
- **Target Population-** Target population in this study is consumers of FMCG products who are located in Alwar.
- **Research Instrument-** In this study, a structured questionnaire has been used for

collection of primary data and with the help of this the objectives of study have been achieved.

DATA TECHNIQUES USED

There are different techniques for analysis of data with the help of SPSS 20. The data has been are as follows:

- Descriptive analysis
- ANOVA
- Regression

DATA ANALYSIS

This study is based on the consumer's online buying behaviour towards FMCG products of HUL and ITC. The consumers have been buying FMCG products online. A sample of 120 consumers have been considered in this study, the data is based on specific demographic variables i.e. age, gender, annual income, educational qualification. Further the online buying behaviour of the consumers has been studied based on their perception towards different products of HUL and ITC under specific segments like personal care, home care and food & beverages.

Table:-1 GENDER OF CONSUMERS

Sr. no.	Gender	No. of consumers	%
1	Male	72	60
2	Female	48	40
Total		120	100

Based on the table above, there are more males i.e. 65% and the females are 35%. This study is focused on consumers who are buying FMCG products online, hence males and females, both the categories of gender have been considered in the study.

Table:-2 AGE OF THE RESPONDENTS

Sr. no.	Age (in years)	No. of consumers	%
1	18 - 25	19	15.8
2	26 - 40	77	64.2
3	41 - 60	24	20
Total		120	100

Based on the table above, there are more consumers who are aged between 26 – 40 years i.e. 77%, followed by 41 – 60 years i.e. 20% and remaining 15.8% are in the age group between 18 – 25 years i.e. 15.8%. The consumers of different age groups have been considered in the study as the requirement and buying behaviour of the consumers change with age.

Table:-3. EDUCATION QUALIFICATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

Sr. no.	Education	No. of consumers	%
1	Graduate	32	26.7
2	Post Graduate	52	43.3
3	Doctorate	36	30
Total		120	100

Based on the above table, there are more consumers who are post graduate i.e. 43.3% followed by Doctorate i.e. 30% and remaining 26.7% are Graduate. In this study, consumers of different educational qualification have been considered since consumers will have a different understanding about the online mode of shopping and even their requirement for FMCG products would be different.

Table:-4 ANNUAL INCOME LEVEL OF THE RESPONDENTS

Sr. no.	Income level	No. of consumers	%
1	Upto 2 Lacs	14	11.7
2	2 - 4 Lacs	49	40.8
3	4 - 6 Lacs	32	26.7
4	Above 6 Lacs	25	20.8
Total		120	100

Based on the above table, there are more consumers who are having an annual income between 2 – 4 Lacs i.e. 40.8%, followed by 4 – 6 Lacs i.e. 26.7%, then above 6 Lacs i.e.

20.8% and remaining 11.7% consumers are having their annual income is upto 2 Lacs. The choice of the consumers towards online buying of FMCG products also change with the income in hand as a person having high salary could afford to buy costly products as compared to those having low salary.

Table:-5 BUY FMCG PRODUCTS ONLINE

Sr. no.	Buy FMCG products online	No. of consumers	%
1	Yes	120	100
2	No		
Total		120	100

In this study only those consumers of FMCG products have been considered who are buying FMCG products online as this study is based on the online buying behaviour of the consumers towards FMCG products. During pandemic the number of consumers who buy FMCG products online have increased to a great extent. In this busy schedule there are many consumers who are preferring to buy FMCG products online as there is no such difference in buying them offline based on the quality rather buying online is somewhat more beneficial as it saves time and even discounts are offered online at times.

Table:-6 LEVEL OF SATISFACTION TOWARDS SHOPPING OF FMCG PRODUCTS ONLINE

Sr. no.	Satisfaction	No. of consumers	%
1	Very high	78	65
2	High	24	20
3	Neutral	2	1.7
4	Low	4	3.3
5	Very Low	12	10
Total		120	100

The above table indicates the level of satisfaction of the consumers towards online buying of FMCG products and there are more number of consumers whose level of satisfaction is very high i.e. 65%, followed by high i.e. 20%, then very low i.e. 10%, then low i.e. 3.3%

and 1.7% consumers have been neutral. The FMCG products are being provided on different e-commerce websites like Big Basket, Grofers, Amazon, and many others and it has become very easy for the consumers to buy FMCG products online with the help of any online mode.

Table:-7 FREQUENCY OF DISCOUNTS BEING PROVIDED BY FMCG COMPANIES IN A MONTH

Sr. no.	Frequency of discounts	No. of consumers	%
1	0 – 2	97	80.8
2	2 – 4	11	9.2
3	4 – 6	4	3.3
4	6 and above	8	6.7
Total		120	100

Based on the table above, there are more consumers who are buying FMCG products online have mentioned that they are being offered discounts 0 – 2 times in a month i.e. 80.8%, followed by 2 – 4 times i.e. 9.2%, 6 and above i.e. 6.7% and 4 – 6 times i.e. 3.3%. The consumers of FMCG products have been buying them online due to many reasons, as such in this busy schedule it becomes very easy to buy FMCG products with a click of a button from home or work place. FMCG products are such that they do not need a check of the quality, rather they are same when bought from a physical store or online.

Table:-8 MONTHLY EXPENSES FOR BUYING FMCG PRODUCTS ONLINE

Sr. no.	Monthly expense for buying FMCG products	No. of consumers	%
1	Less than Rs. 1000	7	5.8
2	Rs. 1000 – 3000	26	21.7
3	Rs. 3000 – 5000	38	31.7
4	More than Rs. 5000	49	40.8
Total		120	100

Based on the table above, there are more consumers who are spending more than Rs. 5000

to buy FMCG products online i.e. 40.8%, followed by Rs. 3000 – 5000 i.e. 31.7%, then Rs. 1000 – 3000 i.e. 21.7% and Less than Rs. 1000 i.e. 5.8%. Online buying behaviour depends on the frequency of buying too, once the consumers are satisfied with the procedure to be followed for online buying of FMCG products, the convenience and other benefits then they increase the amount being spent on buying of FMCG products.

Table:-9 FMCG SEGMENT PREFERRED

Product category	Company	
	ITC	HUL
Personal care		
Soap	2.12	3.78
Fairness cream	2.21	3.48
Hair oil	2.52	3.35
Deodorant	2.58	3.42
Shampoo	2.58	3.50
Hand wash	3.77	2.71
Home care		
Dish wash Bar	2.63	3.51
Floor cleaner	2.58	3.17
Food & Beverages		
Wheat flour	3.71	3.15
Fruit juice	2.93	3.82
Coffee	2.70	3.93
Soup	2.67	3.78

The above table indicates a comparison between products of different categories under personal care i.e. soap, fairness cream, hair oil, deodorant, shampoo and hand wash. A comparative analysis has been made towards the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL. The consumers have been asked to provide response based on 5 point likert scale towards their preference towards online buying of FMCG products ranging from Very high (5) to very low (1). Based on the product category under personal care, soap of HUL like Dove is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the soap of ITC like Vivel etc. etc. Based on the product category under personal care, fairness cream of HUL like Fair &

lovely etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the fairness cream of ITC like Charmis etc. Based on the product category under personal care, hair oil of ITC like Fiama Oil etc. are less preferred by the consumers as compared to the hair oil of HUL like Indulekha etc. Based on the product category under personal care, deodorant of ITC like Engage etc. are less preferred by the consumers as compared to the deodorant of HUL like Axe etc. Based on the product category under personal care, shampoo of ITC like Superia etc. are less preferred by the consumers as compared to the shampoo of HUL like Clinic+ etc. Based on the product category under personal care, hand wash of ITC like Savlon etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the hand wash of HUL like Lifebuoy etc.

Based on the product category under home care, dish wash bar/ liquid of HUL like Vim etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the dish wash liquid of ITC. Based on the product category under home care, floor cleaner of HUL like Domex etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the floor cleaner of ITC like Nimyle etc.

Based on the product category under food & beverages, wheat flour of ITC like Aashirvaad etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the wheat flour of HUL like Annapurna etc. Based on the product category under food & beverages, fruit juice of HUL like Kissan etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the fruit juice of ITC like B Natural etc. Based on the product category under food & beverages, coffee of HUL like Bru etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the coffee of ITC like Sunbean etc. Based on the product category under food & beverages, Soup of HUL like Knorr etc. is more preferred by the consumers as compared to the soup of ITC like ITC Master Chef.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

- H_{01} - There is no significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers

H_{11} - There is a significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers

The significance of the above hypothesis has been tested through Regression using SPSS 20. The independent variable for application of Regression is discounts and the dependent variable is monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.079 ^a	.006	.002	1.124

a. Predictors: (Constant), Discounts

The above table indicates there is low but positive correlation between discounts and the dependent variable is monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers since the value of R is 0.079. The value of R square is 0.006 and this is also quite low. R square is how much the independent variable could explain the dependent variable.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	.941	1	.941	.745	.390 ^b
1	Residual	148.984	118	1.263		
	Total	149.925	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Monthly_exp

b. Predictors: (Constant), Discounts

The significant value indicated in the table above is 0.390 and this is above 0.05 (at 5% level of significance), hence the null hypothesis will be accepted i.e. H₀₁ - There is no significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers and the alternate hypothesis has been rejected i.e. H₁₁ - There is a significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers.

- H₀₂ - There is no significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products

H₂₂ - There is a significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products

The above hypothesis has been tested through ANOVA with the use of SPSS 20. ANOVA is applied when there are more than two groups, and the response of the consumers of FMCG products has been considered towards products of different categories i.e. Personal Care, Home Care and Food & Beverages.

ANOVA

Online buying

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.372	2	.686	.642	.027
Within Groups	381.783	357	1.069		
Total	383.156	359			

The significant value in the above table is 0.027 which is less than 0.05 (at 5% level of significance) and this indicates that the null hypothesis has been rejected

i.e. H_0 - There is no significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products and the alternate hypothesis has been accepted i.e. H_{22} - There is a significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products. The product category differs and accordingly the need of the consumers as food & beverage items are required regularly though the other category of products may not be required so frequently.

FINDINGS

- There are more males than females who have been a part of this study based on online buying of FMCG.
- The consumers of different age groups have been considered in the study as the requirement and buying behaviour of the consumers change with age.
- There are more consumers who are post graduate, followed by Doctorate and then Graduate.
- The choice of the consumers towards online buying of FMCG products also change with the income in hand as a person having high salary could afford to buy costly products as compared to those having low salary.
- There are many consumers who are preferring to buy FMCG products online as there is no such difference in buying them offline based on the quality rather buying online is somewhat more beneficial as it saves time and even discounts are offered online at times.
- It has become very easy for the consumers to buy FMCG products online with the

help of any online mode.

- FMCG products are such that consumers do not need a check of the quality, rather they are same when bought from a physical store or online.
- Once the consumers are satisfied with the procedure to be followed for online buying of FMCG products, the convenience and other benefits then they increase the amount being spent on buying of FMCG products
- Based on the product category under personal care, consumers prefer to buy FMCG products of HUL as compared to that of ITC.
- Based on the product category under home care, consumers prefer to buy FMCG products of HUL as compared to that of ITC.
- Based on the product category under food & beverages, consumers prefer to buy FMCG products of HUL as compared to that of ITC.
- There is no significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers
- There is a significant association between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products.

CONCLUSION:-

FMCG is fourth largest among all the other sectors in India and it contributes significantly to the Gross Domestic Product of India. Majority consumers are buying FMCG products online as they find it quite easy to buy online instead of going to a brick and mortar store. This study is conducted to understand the online buying behavior of consumers towards different FMCG products. The consumers are expecting to get some innovation in the products available in the FMCG sector and this will also encourage many customers to buy these products. FMCG companies has launched lower-priced products for maintaining production and profitability for expansion of consumer base. Online buying behaviour of the consumers has been studied based on their perception towards different products of HUL and ITC under specific segments like personal care, home care and food & beverages. Based on the product category under personal care, home care and food & beverages consumers prefer to buy FMCG products of HUL as compared to that of ITC. There is no significant impact of discounts on monthly expenses on FMCG products by selected consumers. There is a significant association

between the online buying of FMCG products of ITC and HUL based on different categories of products.

SUGGESTIONS:-

- ITC should make an attempt to improve their products under the personal care category besides hand wash, so that the consumers could buy more FMCG products of ITC online.
- More discounts should be given by the companies HUL and ITC, so that more consumers prefer to buy their FMCG products online.
- More branding and promotion should be carried out by the ITC so that their products are preferred more by the consumers.
- ITC should make an attempt to improve their products under the home care category, so that the consumers could buy more FMCG products of ITC online.
- Some more products that vary in cost should be introduced by HUL and ITC so that a different category of consumers could buy them.

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